

PEER REVIEW REPORT

Peer review report for:

Li, S., Longfei, C., Hao, L., Yaxin, J., Wei, G., Jounghyung, C. (2025). Environmental design for coastal protection from a stakeholder perspective: A review from 2000 to 2023. *RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas*, 65(1), e2024-0169. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/S0034-759020250106>

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Disclaimer: The content of the Peer Review Report is the full copy of the reviewers' and authors' reports. Typing and punctuation errors are not edited.

Reviewers:

Wanxin Qian. Anhui University of Science and Technology, Huainan, China.

The second reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

ROUND 1

Reviewer 1 Report

Reviewer: Wanxin Qian

Date review returned: 17-Apr-2024

Recommendation: Minor Revision

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state "none" if this is not applicable)

none

Comments to the Author

1. *What were the reasons for the failure to implement the initial related management and policies mentioned earlier? How were these issues resolved later? If resolved through "stakeholder engagement," what specific form did this participation take, and how was consensus reached and policies implemented on what kind of interactive platform?*

2. *The research objectives previously mentioned assessing the methods of community involvement, but this was less discussed later on. What are the criteria for evaluating the success of “marine conservation”?*
3. *Regarding “Stakeholder Problem-Solving Methods” and “Paradigm Shift: Natural Basis,” is there a need to summarize the results, i.e., assess the different methods at different stages, the pros and cons of different strategies at the same stage, the overall pros and cons at different stages, and the comparative evaluation of different strategies at different stages? This would lead to conclusions as well as future outlooks and trends.*
4. *The article does not specifically elaborate on the shortcomings and limitations of this study, merely discussing related issues, lacking reflection.*
5. *The correlation between research objectives, research purposes, and research results is weak.*
6. *In terms of paragraph logic, the current deficiencies in “coastal protection environmental design” should be highlighted, thereby introducing the necessity and importance of the chosen research topic.*

Reviewer 2 Report

The reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

AUTHORS' RESPONSES

Reviewer: 1

1. *This study is a synthesized theoretical study, about the reasons why the relevant policies failed to be implemented is not in the scope of this paper, and secondly, the analysis of the specific design and practice process of stakeholder participation is not the purpose of this study, for the relevant policies and more specific practice research will be further supplemented and improved in the subsequent research.*
2. *e.ocus on community participation and social factors: recognizing the importance of community participation and social aspects for coastal protection,*
(Deleted content) “The review will analyze how stakeholder engagement affects the success and acceptance of conservation measures.”
3. *“Stakeholder Solutions - Traditional coastal protection strategies in the early 21st century” (added) “This is a more progressive strategic approach than traditional coastal protection strategies, which focus more on the protection of natural ecosystems.”*
Stakeholder Solutions - Seawalls and coastal armor “(added)” Therefore, the widespread use of coastal protection strategies in developed coasts can effectively protect the coast, but the accompanying negative effects can accelerate erosion in neighboring areas.”
4. *“Conclusion - Call for collective action to continue coastal protection research”*
(Added content) “Due to the limitations of the study scope and subjective factors, further research will be strengthened in the follow-up study for the development of coastal protection policies and more specific practices.”

5. e. *Focus on community engagement and social factors: Recognizing the importance of community engagement and social aspects for coastal protection, (delete) “The review will analyse how stakeholder engagement contributes to the success and acceptance of conservation measures.”*

f. *(revised content) “Analysis of effective strategies and design methods: Drawing on feasible design strategies and methods based on successful coastal protection projects in the literature.” (deleted content) “By analysing case studies and successful coastal protection projects, the review will identify” (amended content) “best practices that have been effective in improving coastal resilience and sustainability.”*

6. *By analyzing the design management and policies related to coastal protection, the selected subject sorted out the negative impact of the early traditional technology from the perspective of time, drew the conclusion that the current “coastal protection environmental design” is inadequate, and drew out the design policy based on sustainable development from the macro level, providing theoretical guidance for the relevant environmental design workers.*

Reviewer: 2

1. Included Studies “(modified)”

A keyword search of Web of Science showed that there were no relevant studies directly on the topic of “environmental design and marine conservation”. However, there are indirect studies on the topic of “marine conservation and related design”, which include the keywords “environment”, “design” and “marine conservation”. The keywords “environment”, “design” and “marine protection” are included. In this study, in conjunction with indirect studies on the theme of “marine conservation and related design”.

2. *Be changed to: 1. Research background; 2. The significance of research; 3. Research purpose*

3. *Be changed to: Research design; Research object; Research scope*

4. *The section on “Data Analysis” has been revised into an independent chapter, and the structure of the preceding and following content has been adjusted accordingly.*

5. *(revised content) “To deeply summarize future outlooks and trends, the keyword co-occurrence analysis of relevant literature from 2000 to 2023 is shown in Figure 3. According to this visualization, the main themes of marine protection environment design can be summarized into core research streams such as ecosystem services, climate change, coastal protection, and management.”*

(deleted content) “By sorting out the keywords of related literatures from 2000 to 2023 (Figure 3), the future outlook and trend findings are summarized based on this.”

Add content:

Simultaneously implementing continuous coastal protection policies, strengthening cooperation and knowledge sharing, and placing greater emphasis on ecological protection in coastal environment design will be the mainstream trends in the future.

ROUND 2

Reviewer 1 Report

The reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

Reviewer 2 Report

Reviewer: Wanxin Qian

Date review returned: 25-Jul-2024

Recommendation: Accept

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable)

None

Comments to the Author

I am pleased to see that clear changes and responses have been made based on the previous review comments. The overall quality of the article has improved. I have no further comments.